

The equivalence of gravitational field and time

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Abstract Energy, time and space are basic notions of our current understanding of nature itself. Although these notions were investigated once and again by many pioneering theorists this is not to say that the theoretical and practical problems arising from these notions are solved once and for all. Rather, it might be objected from a critical point of view that there will be nothing new in this regard. In any case, we should not lose sight of this obvious fact energy, time and space are deeply embedded in physical sciences too. For this reason, the relationship between energy time and space is re-investigated again from the view of physics.

Keywords Energy · time · space · unified field theory · causality

1 Introduction

Time itself and the properties of time including various other aspects related to time, have always engaged prominently philosophers, mathematicians [1] and other author. However, time has been especially important at least since the beginning of the 20th Century [2] for physics[3, 4, 5, 6] too. A proper discussion of the issue of time, a further coverage of this topic, an historical overview and a general presentation of the positions of various authors[7] with respect to time is available publicly. Historically, it has been the rise and fall of the Aristotelian dominance of philosophy in Europe which has been superseded hand in hand by an erection of the priority of the calculus in physics by Isaac Newton's (1642–1727) masterpiece *Principia* [1]. The increasingly detailed and pointed exchange on time and space has still not ended and the last word on

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the question what is time, what is space has not been spoken in this respect. On this view, following Plato, Newton, and others, time is something like an empty container into which events, processes et cetera may be placed in. In point of fact, time as such is a kind of a container which exists independently of what if anything at all is placed in it. Newton himself endorsed this reductionist view about time and a motion of bodies which is to be defined relative to absolute time “**Tempus absolutum verum & Mathematicum**” [see 1, p. 5] Following Newton, space itself is absolute too or “**Spatium absolutum ...**” [see 1, p. 5] However, Aristotle, Leibniz and others argued the existence of time as being independent of events which occur in time. In point of fact, especially Leibniz who introduced several lines of attack on Clarke-Newton’s conception of absolute space and time holding instead that true motions are to be defined relatively to each other. The fundamental disagreement between Newton and Leibniz over the true nature of space and time is documented especially by the Leibniz-Clarke correspondence and reached its climax in Leibniz dictum: “**I hold space to be something merely relative, as time is ..**”

Needless to say that such arguments imply the possibility that time as such has had a beginning, and that time as such can have an end. However, such questions about the nature of time appear to be closely connected to physics too. Considering questions like a possible topology or structure of time, it is also worth asking whether time as such can be represented by geometry? In this context it should be noted that a gravitational time dilation[8] is one consequence of Einstein’s relativity theory. The closer a clock to the source of gravitation (lower the gravitational potential), the slower time passes. For atomic clocks at different gravitational potential (i. e. differing altitudes) show different times (recall also Pound - Rebka experiment). In other words, physics is linking during the last one hundred years the behaviour of time directly to gravitation itself. The purpose of this article is to re-investigate the possible principal relationship between the gravitational field and time.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Definitions

Definition 1 Speed of the light c in vacuum.

Let c denote the speed of the light c in vacuum.

Definition 2 Energy ${}_R E_t$

Let ${}_R E_t$ denote the total energy of something from the standpoint of a stationary observer (R) at a certain point (period) in space-time t .

Definition 3 Time ${}_R t_t$

Let ${}_R t_t$ denote the time from the standpoint of a stationary observer (R) at a certain point (period) in space-time t .

Definition 4 Space ${}_R S_t$

Let ${}_R S_t$ denote the mathematical identity between energy (${}_R E_t$) and time (${}_R t_t$) from the standpoint of a stationary observer (R) at a certain point (period) in space-time t . The relationship between ${}_R E_t$ and ${}_R t_t$ is given in general as

$${}_R S_t \equiv ({}_R E_t) + ({}_R t_t) \quad (1)$$

Definition 5 Matter ${}_R M_t$

Matter is determined by energy and vice versa. "Eines der wichtigsten Resultate der Relativitätstheorie ist die Erkenntnis, daß jegliche Energie E eine ihr proportionale Trägheit (E/c^2) besitzt." [9] Let ${}_R M_t$ denote matter (and not only mass) from the standpoint of a stationary observer. The relationship between ${}_R E_t$ and ${}_R M_t$ is given in general as

$${}_R E_t \equiv (c^2 \times {}_R M_t) \quad (2)$$

Definition 6 Gravitational field ${}_R g_t$

Let ${}_R g_t$ denote the gravitational field from the standpoint of a stationary observer (R) at a certain point (period) in space-time t . In general, it is

$${}_R g_t \equiv {}_R U_t - {}_R M_t \quad (3)$$

Definition 7 The notion ${}_R U_t$

Let ${}_R U_t$ denote the mathematical identity between matter (${}_R M_t$) and the gravitational field (${}_R g_t$) from the standpoint of a stationary observer (R) at a certain point (period) in space-time t . The relationship between ${}_R M_t$ and ${}_R g_t$ is given in general as

$${}_R U_t \equiv ({}_R M_t) + ({}_R g_t) \quad (4)$$

Definition 8 The relationship between ${}_R S_t$ and ${}_R U_t$

The relationship between ${}_R S_t$ and ${}_R U_t$ is determined by the equation

$$\frac{{}_R S_t}{{}_R U_t} \equiv c^2 \quad (5)$$

2.2 Axioms

2.3 Axioms in general

Axioms [10] and rules which are chosen carefully can be of use to avoid logical inconsistency and equally preventing science from supporting particular ideologies. Rightly or wrongly, long lasting advances in our knowledge of nature are enabled by suitable axioms [11] too. Einstein himself brings it again to the point. [see 12, p. 17]

“Die wahrhaft großen Fortschritte der Naturerkenntnis sind auf einem der Induktion fast diametral entgegengesetzten Wege entstanden.”[see 12, p. 17]

Einstein’s previous position now been translated into English: *The truly great advances in our understanding of nature originated in a manner almost diametrically opposed to induction*. It is worth mentioning in this matter, Einstein himself advocated especially basic laws (axioms) and conclusions derived from the same as a main logical foundation of any ‘theory’.

**“Grundgesetz (Axiome)
und
Folgerungen
zusammen bilden das was man
eine ‘Theorie’
nennt. ”**[see 12, p. 17]

Albert Einstein’s (1879-1955) message translated into English as: *Basic law (axioms) and conclusions together form what is called a ‘theory’* has still to get round. However, it is currently difficult to ignore completely these historical and far reaching words of wisdom. The same taken more seriously and put into practice, will yield an approach to fundamental scientific problems which is more creative and sustainably logically consistent.

2.4 Axioms in detail

Historically, Aristotle himself already cited **the law of excluded middle** and **the law of contradiction** as examples of axioms. However, why should one axiom be more appropriate than another?

2.4.1 Axiom I. *Lex identitatis*

Nonetheless, **lex identitatis** is an axiom too, which possess the potential to serve as the most basic and equally as the most simple axiom of science. Something which is really just itself is equally different from everything else. In point of fact, is such an equivalence which everything has to itself inherent or must the same be constructed by human mind and consciousness. Following Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716):

“**Chaque chose est ce qu’elle est.**
Et dans autant d’exemples qu’on voudra
A est A, B est B.”[see 13, p. 327]

or $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}$ or $+1 = +1$. In this context, **lex contradictionis**, the negative of *lex identitatis*, or $+0 = +1$ is of no minor importance too.

To say that $+1$ is identical to $+1$ is to say that both are the same.

AXIOM 1. LEX IDENTITATIS.

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (6)$$

However, even such a numerical identity which seems in itself wholly unproblematic, for it indicates just to a relation which something has to itself and nothing else, is still subject to controversy. Another increasingly popular view is that the same numerical identity implies the controversial view that we are talking about two different numbers $+1$. The one $+1$ is on the left side on the equation, the other $+1$ is on the right side of an equation. The basicness of the relation of identity implies the contradiction too while circularity is avoided. In other words, how can the same $+1$ be identical with itself and be equally different from itself? We may usefully state that identity is an utterly problematic notion and might be the most troublesome of all.

2.4.2 Axiom II. *Lex contradictionis*

AXIOM 2. LEX CONTRADICTIONIS.

$$+0 \equiv +1 \quad (7)$$

A considerable obstacle to understanding contemporary usage of the term contradiction, however, is that contradiction does not seem to be a unitary one. How can something be both, itself (**a path is a straight line** from the standpoint of a co-moving observer at a certain point in space-time) **and** the other of itself, its own opposition (**the same path is not a straight line**, the same path is curved, from the standpoint of a stationary observer **at a certain point in space-time**) [14]. We may simply deny the existence of objective or of any other contradictions. Furthermore, even if it remains

especially according to Einstein's special theory of relativity that it is not guaranteed that the notion of an absolute contradiction is justified, Einstein's special theory of relativity insist that contradictions are objective and real. That this is so highlights the fact that from the standpoint of a co-moving observer, under certain circumstances, **a path is a straight line** and nothing else. However, under the same circumstances of special theory of relativity where the relative velocity $v > 0$, from the standpoint of a stationary observer **the same path is a not a straight line, the path is curved**. The justified question is, why should and how can an identical be a contradictory too?

2.4.3 Axiom III. Lex negationis

AXIOM 3. LEX NEGATIONIS.

$$\neg(+0) = (+1) \tag{8}$$

where \neg denotes the (natural/logical) process of negation.

3 Results

3.1 Theorems

Theorem 1 (*The identity and the interaction between energy and time.*)

If the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (9)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$+1 \equiv \frac{{}_R E_t}{{}_R S_t} + \frac{{}_R t_t}{{}_R S_t} \quad (10)$$

is also true, the absence of (any technical) errors presupposed.

Proof The premise (see axiom 2.4.1)

$$+1 = +1 \quad (11)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by ${}_R S_t$ it is

$$(+1) \times {}_R S_t = (+1) \times {}_R S_t \quad (12)$$

or

$${}_R S_t = {}_R S_t \quad (13)$$

Adding the term $-({}_R E_t) + ({}_R E_t) = 0$ on both sides of the equation before, it is

$${}_R S_t + 0 = {}_R S_t - ({}_R E_t) + ({}_R E_t) \quad (14)$$

Our understanding of the relationship between energy and time is determined by the assumption that **all but energy is time**. In other words, there is no third between energy and time, a third is not given. Time is the complementary of energy and vice versa. Energy is the complementary of time. Each of both is equally the complementary of its own other. We **define**

$${}_R t_t \equiv {}_R S_t - {}_R E_t \quad (15)$$

Substituting this relationship into the equation before, it is

$${}_R S_t = {}_R E_t + {}_R t_t \quad (16)$$

Normalising the relationship between energy and time we obtain

$$+1 \equiv \frac{{}_R E_t}{{}_R S_t} + \frac{{}_R t_t}{{}_R S_t} \quad (17)$$

□

Theorem 2 (*The identity and the interaction between matter and gravitational field.*)

If the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (18)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$+1 \equiv \frac{{}_R M_t}{{}_R U_t} + \frac{{}_R g_t}{{}_R U_t} \quad (19)$$

is also true, the absence of (any technical) errors presupposed.

Proof The premise (see axiom 2.4.1)

$$+1 = +1 \quad (20)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by ${}_R S_t$ it is

$$(+1) \times {}_R U_t = (+1) \times {}_R U_t \quad (21)$$

or

$${}_R U_t = {}_R U_t \quad (22)$$

Adding the term $-({}_R M_t) + ({}_R M_t) = 0$ on both sides of the equation before, it is

$${}_R U_t + 0 = {}_R U_t - ({}_R M_t) + ({}_R M_t) \quad (23)$$

Our understanding of the relationship between matter and gravitational field is impacted by Einstein's train of thoughts on this relationship. Einstein wrote:

“Wir unterscheiden im folgenden zwischen ‘Gravitationsfeld’ und ‘Materie’ in dem Sinne, daß alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet wird, also nicht nur die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne, sondern auch das elektromagnetische Feld.” [see 4, p. 802/803]

Einstein's position translated into English:

We make a distinction hereafter between ‘gravitational field’ and ‘matter’ in this way that everything but the gravitational field is termed as ‘matter’ that is to say not only ‘matter’ in the ordinary sense, but the electromagnetic field as well.

Following Einstein, matter and gravitational field are complementary to each other. In other words, **all but gravitational field is matter** or there is no third between matter and gravitational field, a third is not given. Matter is the complementary of gravitational field and vice versa. The gravitational field is the complementary of matter. Again, each of both is equally the complementary of its own other. The following figure may illustrate this relationship in more detail.

Fig. 1. Matter and gravitational field.

As already **defined** before, it is

$${}_R g_t \equiv {}_R U_t - {}_R M_t \quad (24)$$

Substituting this relationship into the equation before, it is

$${}_R U_t = {}_R M_t + {}_R g_t \quad (25)$$

Normalising the relationship between matter and gravitational field we obtain

$$+1 \equiv \frac{{}_R M_t}{{}_R U_t} + \frac{{}_R g_t}{{}_R U_t} \quad (26)$$

□

Theorem 3 (*The equivalence of gravitational field and time.*)

If the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (27)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$${}_R t_t \equiv (c^2 \times {}_R g_t) \quad (28)$$

is also true, the absence of (any technical) errors presupposed.

Proof The premise (see axiom 2.4.1)

$$+1 = +1 \quad (29)$$

is true. Substituting Eq. 17 into this equation we obtain

$$\frac{{}_R E_t}{{}_R S_t} + \frac{{}_R t_t}{{}_R S_t} \equiv +1 \quad (30)$$

Substituting Eq. 26 into Eq. 30 we obtain

$$\frac{{}_R E_t}{{}_R S_t} + \frac{{}_R t_t}{{}_R S_t} \equiv \frac{{}_R M_t}{{}_R U_t} + \frac{{}_R g_t}{{}_R U_t} \quad (31)$$

Multiplying Eq. 31 by the term ${}_R S_t$ it is

$$\frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R E_t}{{}_R S_t} + \frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R t_t}{{}_R S_t} \equiv \frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R M_t}{{}_R U_t} + \frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R g_t}{{}_R U_t} \quad (32)$$

or

$${}_R E_t + {}_R t_t \equiv \frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R M_t}{{}_R U_t} + \frac{{}_R S_t \times {}_R g_t}{{}_R U_t} \quad (33)$$

According to the definition 8 it is $\frac{{}_R S_t}{{}_R U_t} \equiv c^2$. Substituting this relationship into equation 33 we obtain

$${}_R E_t + {}_R t_t \equiv (c^2 \times {}_R M_t) + (c^2 \times {}_R g_t) \quad (34)$$

According to the definition 5 it is ${}_R E_t \equiv (c^2 \times {}_R M_t)$. Substituting this relationship into equation 34 it is

$${}_R E_t + {}_R t_t \equiv {}_R E_t + (c^2 \times {}_R g_t) \quad (35)$$

Simplifying equation 35 it is

$${}_R t_t \equiv (c^2 \times {}_R g_t) \quad (36)$$

In other words, gravitational field (${}_R g_t$) and time (${}_R t_t$) are more or less equivalent. \square

4 Discussion

The equivalence of gravitational field and time is based on several assumptions.

Firstly. The definition $\frac{{}_R S_t}{{}_R U_t} \equiv c^2$ is part of this insight. However, such a definition is allowed, logically sound and does not require any further proof.

Secondly. In contrast to such a definition, the assumption of the equivalence not only of mass and energy but of matter and energy needs a kind of a proof but is to some extent already proofed[9, 15, 16]. In other words, matter is equal to energy and vice versa energy is equal to matter or ${}_R M_t \equiv \frac{{}_R E_t}{c^2}$. In point of fact, the total energy (${}_R E_t$) from the standpoint of a stationary observer is determined by the relativistic potential energy (${}_P E_t$) and the relativistic kinetic energy (${}_K E_t$) or '*vis viva*'[17, 18] as demanded by Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646 - 1716) as ${}_R E_t \equiv ({}_P E_t) + ({}_K E_t)$ which justifies according to Einstein [9] the equivalence of matter and energy.

5 Conclusions

By our obvious willingness not to give up and to learn from nature and also over hundred if not thousands of years of experience in science it was possible to snatch another secret from the unknown. In fact, one might reasonably accept **the equivalence of gravitational field and time.**

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